

JERRY GARCIA'S TRIBUTE TO PAUL KLEE'S *TWITTERING MACHINE*

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SUMMARY

Paul Klee and Jerry Garcia both aspired to art and music in their youth, Klee choosing to pursue art seriously while enjoying musical performance, and Garcia the opposite. Garcia's small drawing noted as a tribute to Paul Klee translates elements of *Twittering Machine* into a derivative but not imitative work: *Like Twittering Machine (For Paul Klee)*. Klee's inscriptions of the title of the drawing juxtapose machine and twittering. Arthur Danto's comments on *Twittering Machine* suggest a reading contrary to the more common perception that the birds are driven by the machine. Klee's *Concert on the Branch* shows the same drawing, minus the machine, and the birds expressively engaged in their singing. Gilles Deleuze's theory of diagrams serves to separate the elements of machine and birds in the drawing. Musical compositions inspired by the drawing alternatively portray mechanical bird noises musically or explore how musicians can emulate natural bird noises. Paying particular attention to the graphic content of the two works of art, we can see Garcia's composition as free interpretation of Klee's original, transposed to depict members of an electric guitar and drum band. Klee's drawing in turn can then be seen as depicting, metaphorically, a string quartet. A reproduction of Klee's drawing appears in a central section of Deleuze and Félix Guattari's *A Thousand Plateaus*, where it is emblematic of the connection in that text between the abstract machine and the refrain.

Jerry Garcia (1942–1995) was an American musician who was the leader and co-founder of the Grateful Dead, a rock 'n' roll band that flourished with improvisational concert performances for thirty years until Garcia's death. Like Paul Klee, Garcia was enthusiastic about both music and art in his youth, having chosen to pursue music, with art as his personal side interest – the opposite of Klee's choice. Garcia revived that interest in art during the last ten years of his life, during which he created hundreds of works of art, including a small drawing inspired by Klee's *Twittering Machine*. Looking carefully at the de-

tails of Klee's drawing and Garcia's drawing one can see how Garcia meant his as a tribute and an interpretation. Whereas most commentary on *Twittering Machine* as well as musical compositions inspired by it perceive the Klee drawing depicting mechanical birds, Garcia's tribute depicts musicians, metaphorically rendered as birds. Examining carefully how Klee titles his drawing and taking a cue from Arthur Danto's brief observations about the drawing, one can see how the Klee drawing, too, can be seen as about musicians, metaphorically rendered as birds.

Fig. 1
 Jerry Garcia, *Like Twittering Machine (For Paul Klee)*, 1985, ink and watercolor on paper, 12,7 x 17,8 cm, Estate of Jerry Garcia
 © Courtesy Deborah Koons Garcia, Photo: Dennis Rothermel

ARTIST-MUSICIAN JERRY GARCIA

As a boy, Jerry Garcia loved singing and drawing.¹ Coping with asthma gave him time to spend drawing, particularly cartoons.² He applied himself seriously, practicing for hours a day, understanding doing art not simply as something to do but which defined you existentially.³ He attended art school briefly as a teenager, but his growing interest in music supplanted his visual artistic impulses, though he carried a sketchbook with him tucked away in his guitar case wherever he went on tour and always.⁴ His interest in art rekindled during the last ten years of his life. Gallery and museum exhibitions of Garcia's work commenced in 1991 and have occurred occasionally since in the US, Japan, and France.⁵ Showing a seemingly ravenous hunger for and expanse of expression, his explorations were in pen and ink, watercolor, acrylic, gouache, etchings, and digital art. Some of his art shows the influence imitatively of Robert Crumb, Claude Monet, George Herriman, Frank Stella, and Paul Klee.⁶

Without reverting to singular traits, Garcia's art encompasses figurative and abstract; heavy compositions with saturated hues; short-hatched lines from which an image emerges, the faintest suggestion of subject through a few deft strokes; clear homages to cartoonists and artists; and without trace of cliché or hurried technique. About 500 individual works remain in the estate.⁷ The publication of *Jerry Garcia: The Collected Artwork* encompasses 225 reproductions.⁸

PAUL KLEE'S TWITTERING MACHINE

Like Twittering Machine (For Paul Klee), 1985 (FIG. 1),⁹ is like Paul Klee's *Twittering Machine*, 1922, 151. It is smaller – 5" x 7" compared to 16" x 12" – and wider than tall rather than vice versa. Klee's drawing is "[o]il transfer drawing, watercolor, and ink on paper with gouache and ink borders on board."¹⁰ Garcia's drawing is "[i]nk and watercolor on paper."¹¹ Were it not for Garcia's title, it would be unlikely that anyone would associate this item with the Klee drawing. Nevertheless, if we look carefully

at what Garcia has conjured up as a tribute to the famous Klee drawing, we can elucidate Garcia's unique and penetrating reading of it by way of comparison.

Knowing nothing more about Paul Klee and his work than we can see in the drawing, such as would approximate Jerry Garcia's encounter with it, Klee's thin-line stick-figure depiction in ink, watercolor, and oil transfer shows four birds in a row on a wire-thin irregularly-curved perch attached to a crank mechanism (FIG. 2).

The hand crank at the right end of the mechanism suggests, in reference to the drawing's title, that as one would crank the birds would twitter. The crank handle is the one detail in the drawing that unambiguously imparts what it signifies – by its

shape and the cross-hatching suggesting a grip surface. The crank is attached to a straight-line wire-thin horizontal shaft, which connects with the perch at the right end. The shaft extends past the end of the perch to the left, where it fits through a round grommet-guide attached to a vertical stake fixed from below. Another round grommet-guide at the far left attaches to a stake fixed from above. A U-shaped brace attaches below to either side of the guide in the middle. The left end of the perch rests loosely in the curve of this U-brace. Thus, as the shaft would be cranked, the perch would rotate in sync with the shaft, though that would turn the curved perch up and around in opposite directions on either end of the perch.

The wingless birds consist of hardly more than a round head attached to a spindly body and legs, with a stroke or several to indicate a tail. The figures do not so much clearly depict birds as they do not easily evoke anything else. The bird heads are simple and flat, with a small eye in the corner opposite an open mouth that emits a shape one takes to be its bird call. The one on the far left stands tallest, with its head pointed skyward. Its open mouth is wedge-shaped, drawn with straight lines and pointed at the edges of the mouth. A long, inverted, perfectly-formed droplet dangles above, centered in the bird's open mouth. There is a small upward tuft of lines around its neck, and a longer cloak of downward lines below that. Two long, not-quite-perfectly-straight-line legs end in three-toed feet that clutch the perch below. A tail of three long lines curled upward at the end extends from the base of the legs.

The second figure has a slightly oblong shape to its downward-turned head, and a curved open mouth. The thin line that is its body juts through to the top of the head. Small streams of dots fan out below the eye, and into the space below. A small, curled, thickened line dangles from its

Fig. 2
Paul Klee, *Die Zwitscher-Maschine* [*The Twittering Machine*], 1922, 151, oil transfer drawing and watercolor on paper on cardboard, 41,3 x 30,5 cm, The Museum of Modern Art, New York, Purchase DIGITAL IMAGE © 2023, The Museum of Modern Art/Scala, Florence

mouth. This bird has three straight-line limbs of uneven length, the middle one of which we can take to be a tail. They each extend to the perch, where, less distinctly, its three-toed feet on its two legs grasp the perch. The two legs cut across the legs of the birds to the left and right.

The third bird from the left is taller than the second, but not quite as tall as the first. It, too, has three limbs, with the outer two crossing over the other birds' legs, and likewise clutching the perch with three-toed feet. Its head is turned to the left and tilted down by 30 degrees. Its mouth is more like that of the first, i.e., not curved; but the part of the head on either side of the open mouth is shaded in. That could indicate the bird's beak, of the sort that a parrot has, not jutting out from the head. The other birds do not have beaks of any sort. The line of the body extends all the way to the top of the third bird's head, and a separate line spirals down from the back of the head two and a half times around the body. A single short, thick line extends from its open mouth, curving gently upwards.

The fourth bird is short, like the second one; its two outer feet grasp the perch with three-toed feet; and the middle one extends below the perch, with indistinct clusters at its end. The fourth bird's head is turned to the right and tilted up by 30 degrees. Streams of dots flow from the back of its head into the space to the left. Its mouth opening is curved, like the second bird, and out of its mouth emanates a straight, thick, barbed line tapering to a fine point at its end.

One could take the figures that emanate from the birds' mouths to be their tongues, or as symbols of their manner of expression.¹² The stake that holds the grommet-guide for the shaft rests below upon the intersection of two perpendicular lines that stretch across a roughly rectangular pink area below the bird-perch-and-wire-shaft construction above. Part

way down that stake there are two blue-gray triangles opposite each other on either side of the stake. The background of the picture is an amorphous field of dull blue and violet, and pink again at the very top. There is what looks like water seepage in upper right-hand corner. There are vague forms in this background where the pigment is darker, a product of the oil transfer process that makes the effective space of the drawing disorienting:

"[T]he subtle chromatic gradations and their varying opacities lead the eye to circulate through space in a manner exactly counter to the directed gaze encouraged by the perspectival devices of naturalistic pictorial space."¹³

The birds, the perch they rest upon, and the crank mechanism thus seem suspended freely and not belonging to any Cartesian space:

"As a result, the drawing seems to emerge from the surrounding space despite the fact that it actually was applied beforehand."¹⁴

The drawing has a mottled, uneven border, narrower on one side than the other. Splotches randomly distributed on the surface of the board could suggest having been stored and forgotten leaning against another drawing, which left black ink impressions from having rubbed against the board. The uneven border, the water stain, the vague outlines in the background, and the splotches deliberately underscore the object's lack of ostentation. Four short pegs demarcate the right and left ends of the pink rectangle, and two where the crossing lines that support the upward stake. However much those pegs would suggest that the pink area is a platform, lines from the top (or far) side of the pink area extend down, alternatively suggesting a pit.

The flimsy, rickety contraption of the crank, shaft, and perch instills little confidence in its functionality. Were it to work somehow – the crank rotating the shaft

and perch – the birds would need to re-set their toes clutching on the perch continuously as the curved perch would swerve up and down, back and forth around the shaft beginning with even the first rotation. The curving perch would also bind around the shaft with each rotation. It is not at all clear how the crank rotating the shaft and perch would cause the birds to twitter. So far as the drawing suggests, the mechanism is at rest, there is no hand on the crank handle, which is positioned down and at rest where gravity would place it, and yet the birds are all singing.

HOW TWITTERING MACHINE IMPARTS MEANING

In Peircean semiotic terms, the simply-drawn crank handle connected to the shaft is an icon, which is “the diagrammatic sign or *icon*, which exhibits a similarity or analogy to the subject”.¹⁵ The bird heads and bird toes adequately resemble what they represent but less distinctively so, and the organic irregularity of the perch makes it resemble a tree branch. The small figures that emerge from the birds’ mouths we can easily take as symbolic of their bird calls rather than depicting visible objects, i.e., representations “which upon being presented to the mind

– without any resemblance to its object and without any reference to a previous convention – calls up a concept”.¹⁶ Klee’s 1920 cartoon of a tenor likewise depicts the sound of the singer’s singing graphically (FIG. 3).

That it looks as if the drawing had rubbed up against another, leaving black textured splotches, and that it looks like the upper right-hand corner had suffered water damage would be *indexical* signification of those effects had they indeed been caused that way: “[a]n index represents its object by a real correspondence with it – as a tally does quarts of milk, and a vane the wind”.¹⁷ Whether or not that is how Klee had administered those effects, that the result allows us to *perceive it as showing* neglect and damage renders the splotches and water damage as thus *symbolically indexical*. This preliminary analysis of the signification of the drawing in terms of Peircean icon, index, and symbol will give us a sense of the layered conceptual complexity of how Klee composes this work – enough such that the Peircean analysis has to bend and combine its basic categories. The spare, abstract line-drawing floating before an undifferentiated backdrop engenders a pervasive vagueness of signification that invites liberal association of meaning. Contributing to that vagueness is the Escheresque geometrical anomaly of the pink area below – is it platform or pit? The drawn image is completely flat, without perspective or visual depth. In all, the drawing ardently defies coherent space. Noting that Klee allows for vagueness “when there is a real inner need,” we can probe how the drawing abides signification nevertheless.¹⁸ One has in this layering of disparate elements of figuration ample demonstration of the inventive versatility of Klee’s drawing styles. It also exemplifies how he aspired to create musical polyphony in art.¹⁹

We can see the drawing in the art work as consisting of three elements: the crank

Fig. 3
Paul Klee, *Der Heldentenor als Konzertsänger* [*The Heroic Tenor as Concert Singer*], 1922, 144, oil transfer drawing and watercolor on paper on cardboard, 28,3 x 39,1 cm, Private Collection
Image credits: Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Archive

contraption, the perch that the birds rest upon, and the four birds. Were it not for the easily discernible crank handle, it would be difficult to see the rest of the connected lines as depicting a machine with a shaft and supports. The crank machine is no more than a diagram, one that suggests the bare essentials of how such a machine could be constructed and how it could work, but without anything more than diagrammatic representation, in effect, “a blueprint to make your own twittering machine”.²⁰ The drawing of the machine comprises simple lines that vaguely indicate its parts and function; how the component parts have specific dimensions of thickness or length or connecting joints does not matter. The perch that the four birds’ toes clutch shows organic rough irregularity. It curves down initially from the right, then up past the machine shaft, then down past the shaft, and finally back up through the U-brace. There is a faint continuation of the perch to the left, curving back up above the shaft. Though still drawn with a thin line, the perch is rendered figuratively but somewhat naturally: rough, irregular, and curving. The drawing of the birds shows figurative representations: heads, eyes, mouths, bodies, limbs, toes, decipherable small details, and postures. Except for their heads, which have no depth, the birds are stick-figures. These drawings are both considerably less than natural renditions of birds and cartoonishly embellishing natural bird-form.

The combined drawing thus consists of divergent and irreducible elements: functional diagram, natural rendition, and cartoon figures. It is a combination that affirms how Gilles Deleuze characterizes Klee’s art as embracing both chaos and childlike simplicity, in contrast to the neat containments of Klee’s contemporaries, Wassily Kandinsky and Piet Mondrian.²¹ Deleuze and Guattari assert that a diagram is *deterritorialized* and thus cannot

be index, icon, or symbol.²² Understood as a diagram, the drawing in *Twittering Machine* in its three elements takes us away from real objects and directs us – “pilots” us – toward what lies beyond the real, toward what Deleuze and Guattari call an “abstract machine”:

“Defined diagrammatically [...], an abstract machine is neither infrastructure that is determining in the last instance nor a transcendental Idea [Idée transcendante] that is determining in the supreme instance. Rather, it plays a piloting role. The diagrammatic or abstract machine does not function to represent, even something real, but rather constructs a real that is yet to come, a new type of reality.”²³

Klee’s lifelong friend and biographer, Will Grohmann, suggests that visits to “workshops” featuring “mechanical contraptions [...] encouraged him to invent weird apparatus such as the ostensible mechanism depicted in *Twittering Machine* [...] which would be wound up with such a handle to make nightingales sing”.²⁴ There is, among the commentaries on the drawing, an inclination to assume that the mechanism of the crank causes the birds to twitter.²⁵ Klee’s title tells us that the drawing depicts a machine that twitters – or does it? In Klee’s hand-written title on the matting below the mounted drawing, in three widely-spaced words with a horizontal mark in the middle, we read:

“Die Zwitscher – Maschine”

As a compound noun in standard construction, the title takes the gender of the last component in the compound: “*Die Zwitschermaschine*”. Grohmann states the title this way.²⁶ Obviously, Klee did not do that exactly, though he does employ standard construction of compound nouns often enough in other titles. Standard construction would not employ a hyphen between the noun components of the compound, and only the first letter of the compound would be capitalized. Further, that

horizontal mark in the middle could be a hyphen, which would suggest a compound noun, or it could be a dash, which would not suggest a compound noun. At any rate, Klee sets the two parts of the compound noun apart from each other. Interestingly, though not clearly evident in all reproductions of the drawing:

“Die Zwitscher . Maschine” is scrawled directly onto the canvas in the upper right corner in a gently curving arc. The title that Klee inscribes onto the drawing itself provides a clearer indication that the drawing *juxtaposes* twittering with a machine, rather than twittering *combined with* or *absorbed into* a machine. That implication would suggest that the horizontal mark in the title below the drawing is a dash, not a hyphen.

In his essay on the occasion of the massive Museum of Modern Art retrospective on the artist’s work in 1987,²⁷ Arthur Danto reminds us that Klee’s art is comical, of the sort of humor that gets people to smile:²⁸

“The tiny joke implanted in [any of Klee’s works] detonates as a piece of agreeable metaphysics – one feels good in the universe – and reinforces a bond of shared values with the artist. Klee does whatever he can to lodge his points [...].”²⁹ Danto underscores how Klee’s humor encompasses his deliberate titles: “[O]f course the marvelous titles, which explain the meanings of the images and complete the joke.”³⁰

For *Die Zwitscher – Maschine*, the joke resonates in the syntactical ambiguity of the title.

So, the drawing does *not* univocally depict mechanical birds – but, then, there is no clear connection between the potential rotation of the crank and shaft and the birds’ twittering. It is a simple machine of sorts – somewhat ridiculously constructed and devoid of clear function or purpose. There are birds resting on the apparatus, and they emit sounds. That is,

small abstract figures appear in the birds’ open mouths, which we take to represent their bird calls. As Danto points out, “a quartet of screwy birds” rests on the machine:

“But the twittering is not produced by the machine, it just happens as a benign coincidence. The machine is inert.”³¹

So, the perhaps most immediately available reading of the drawing that it depicts mechanical birds does not make sense. That reading renders the machine active and the birds’ singing the passive effect. But if we note, as Danto does, that the machine is at rest, then it is the machine that is the passive element of the drawing and the birds who sing are active and intentional. Danto suggests further that “Klee is making some kind of point about the futility of machines,” “[o]r perhaps he is saying it might not be a bad thing if we bent our inventive gifts to the artificial generation of bird songs.”³² The divergence of that disjunction underscores how open the drawing is to imaginative reading. It would perhaps best seem that there is a crank handle connected to a shaft, which is the machine part, and there are birds, who rest on a perch and not the shaft, and who twitter. Those are the concrete parts of the signification of the drawing, and the remainder of its composition is loosely amenable to inventive interpretation, and no doubt intentionally so. Commentators on the drawing qualify their interpretations honestly as “perfectly plausible,” “apparently,” “suggesting,” or what it “looks like”.

Klee’s drawing, *Twittering Machine*, has a place explicitly in Deleuze and Guattari’s expansive text, *A Thousand Plateaus*.³³ Its image appears inaugurating an important section of the text. That section of the text mentions Klee repeatedly, but mostly in reference to Klee’s theoretical writings.³⁴ There is no discussion of *Twittering Machine*. But the drawing does simultaneously illustrate two important concepts:

the machine – “always singular keys that open or close an assemblage [agencement], a territory” – and the refrain – “any aggregate of matters of expression that draws a territory and develops into territorial motifs and landscapes”.³⁵ Ian Buchanan shows how *complex* rather than *assemblage* would serve better as a translation of Deleuze and Guattari’s use of *agencement*.³⁶ The abstract machine underlying how a bird designates territory in its singing refrain is firmed up in its repetition. Likewise, how crowds of sports fans chant or sing anthems for their teams reveals the abstract machine that triggers the assemblage of loyalty and affiliation to the team. In each case it is the refrain that reveals and strengthens the underlying abstract machine, which otherwise is not visible or audible. As well, Deleuze and Guattari invoke the observation of composer and ornithologist Olivier Messiaen that birdcalls show “autonomous” “invented” refrains revealing “not only virtuosos but artists”.³⁷ The point is that the connection between the audible refrain and the underlying not visible abstract machine is not fixed and immutable. The relationship is bidirectional – the constantly variable refrain determines and evolves the machine as much as the machine inspires the refrain. And so, this is what is particularly emblematic about *Twittering Machine* for Deleuze and Guattari – the layered and ambiguously connected or not connected relationship between the simple functional design of the contraption with the oddly-placed perch and the active singing of the four birds exactly depicts the tenuous efficacy and available expressiveness of an abstract machine underlying a refrain.

HOW LIKE TWITTERING MACHINE (FOR PAUL KLEE) DERIVES FROM TWITTERING MACHINE

Garcia’s *Like Twittering Machine (For Paul Klee)* includes seven birds, the largest of which stands alone to the left of the others (FIG. 1). It is an ostrich-like bird, with a round plump body, an array of stubby tail feathers, flowering curlicues gathered around the base of its long neck, more half-way up, and a tuft of crown feathers sticking up out of the top of its head, which altogether somewhat replicates the adornment on the left-most bird in the Klee drawing. Its head turns behind to the left. Arrayed in semi-circular rows beyond its open mouth are simple repetitive small marks against a bright yellow background. So, it chatters incessantly, and its chattering emanates outwards from its open beak. A large wind-up key sticks up out of its back. Like Klee’s crank, the wind-up key is motionless, there is no hand gripping it, and it is unclear how it affects the bird. The big bird is connected to an extended line drawing to the right with a zig-zag line such as represents a resistor in a circuit diagram. The continuous line contraction follows down below and then over to the right, and upwards as well. The linear contraction incorporates more pseudo-electrical-circuit-diagram figures, spirals, balance scales, an inverted bowl, wheels, and various indistinct elements.

There are six more birds, some very small, with open mouths and twitter-indicators emanating out around their open mouths. They all have beaks, and some have minimal indications of having wings. Yet, these are stick-figures with minimal indication of girth, like Klee’s birds, and there is likewise no indication of depth.

As with *Twittering Machine*, this is a non-dimensional realm. The sound-emanating indicators surround parts of the contraption and generally float around. There is more of the yellow background to the right, with the next-to-largest bird thus creating nearly as much twittering. Short, dark even brush strokes cover the lower section of the drawing. Garcia's birds are slightly more substantial than Klee's, having round bodies, but Garcia does retain the non-three-dimensional simple drawings: stick figures with some indications of body parts. Aside from sketch-book practice replications of the semi-stick-figures from George Herri-man's *Krazy Kat*, this is a drawing style not found elsewhere in Garcia's art.³⁸

Klee was one of the artists that Garcia studied and admired.³⁹ Garcia's tribute to Klee is evocative of *Twittering Machine*, but without copying any specific part. There are birds emitting what we take to be sounds, but the birds are different in having minimal two-dimensional shape and their sounds are different in emanating broadly. The birds are different in number, relative size, and arrangement. In place of the curious preposterous kinetic machine, there is a curious preposterous electrical circuit design. For what Klee's drawing is about, Garcia gets it, in the way that one gets a good sly joke, and he shows how he gets it by transforming it into something parallel, or, by telling the joke differently. It is something like a cover of another performer's song – identifiably derivative of the original but distinctive in how this version of the song elicits our appreciative recollection of the original while embellishing without detracting from it. Implicitly, Garcia's *Like Twittering Machine (For Paul Klee)* tells us how Garcia sees the Klee drawing – how a musician reads the drawing, or, at least, how this one musician reads this drawing.

MUSICAL COMPOSITIONS INSPIRED BY *TWITTERING MACHINE*

Like Garcia, Paul Klee was drawn towards both music and art in his youth, but he resolved to choose art.⁴⁰ Klee's home life growing up and as an adult was full of music.⁴¹ He saw the connection between art and music in interesting ways, and this topic has been explored at length.⁴² Some "works depict playing and making music," some evoke "basic musical concepts," and some "envision *the musical structure of the pictorial*," or treat musical "scores as drawings and drawings as scores," or provide a "reading and [...] interpretation" to capture "the sounding of [the] melodic line," or offer "works [...] that could be played," or create "the strokes of a brush or a pencil [...] as the same as the strokes in the air made by a playing bow" of a violin.⁴³ Klee's connection of music and art is intimately intricate such that one cogent summation asserts with appropriate vagueness "that the relation between painting and music in Klee's work can only be understood from the one coming to the other and one becoming the other."⁴⁴ Maybe, though, *Twittering Machine* provides yet another sort of this connection. Klee's art has directly inspired commemorative music, including treatments of *Twittering Machine*. Gunther Schuller's *Seven Studies on Themes of Paul Klee* (1959) includes a two-and-a-half-minute-long segment, *Twittering Machine*.⁴⁵ It begins with French horns and violas playing sixteenth notes in tightly oscillating figures thus buzzing like swarming bees, in the manner of Nikolai Rimsky-Korsakov's *Flight of the Bumblebee* (1899–1900). Then single notes follow, or repeated notes without inflection. Notes are unconnected by melodic line, played by flute, piccolo, reeds, and muted flutter-tongue brass, wood block, and gourd.

Peeps, chirps, trills without connecting articulation continue as if the stilted mechanical effects of an organ grinder, music box, or player-piano. As Schuller explains, there is a gradual *ritardando* in the music as the machine runs down, and then a quick return to original tempo as it is re-wound.⁴⁶ It is music performed mechanically and inexpressively, not as any skilled musician would ordinarily perform music.

Drawing from Siglind Bruhn's analysis, we can see how the third movement of Peter Maxwell Davies' *Five Klee Pictures* (1959–1976) addresses the *Twittering Machine*.⁴⁷ Following Bruhn's analysis further: four separate instrumental groups intone repetitive phrases and some improvisational components; a steady bass line in $\frac{3}{4}$ time, thus cyclically, underscores the cranking of the machine; the separate groups all become louder and increasingly cacophonous, as the tempo accelerates; and there is a sudden pause, suggesting that the cranking stops, and then it resumes as it had begun, slowly and more softly.

Drawing again from Bruhn's analysis, Giselher Klebe's composition, *Die Zwitschermaschine*, divides into four parts, each corresponding to one of the four birds, and reflecting what can be gleaned from the individual postures of the birds.⁴⁸ Following Bruhn further: the mechanistic command of how each bird might twitter places each part in the context of the machine.

Tan Dun's orchestral rendering of *Twittering Machine* has musicians using their instruments percussively.⁴⁹ String instruments are fingered heavily without bowing, plucking *pizzicato* behind the bridge, and bouncing the wood part of the bow on the strings. Brass instruments are played by slapping the mouthpiece with the palm of the hand or played with just the mouthpiece. Reed instruments are played with just the reed. Flute and piccolo play random glissandos. Small, percussive instru-

ments include whistle, ratchet, güiro, sleigh bells, and maracas. Mostly, this tapestry of percussive effects consists in singular peeps, chirps, and guttural bird-like noises. Explicitly marked in the score as "twittering" is vocalization by the musicians in unison: "chi-k chi-k" and "tch tch". String instruments bowing normally effect birds flitting about, and reed and brass instruments just fingering their instruments noisily without playing effects birds ruffling their feathers. More overtly than Schuller, Tan Dun realizes emulation of *bird* noises without suggesting mechanization, with the exception of the ratchet and güiro percussive noises, which do sound mechanical.

Niklaus Erismann has composed *Zirp-Maschine* drawing upon Karl Heinz Stockhausen's Plus-Minus methods of sound organization.⁵⁰ Erismann used a computer MIDI to simulate piano trills, brief serialist melodies, and dissonant chords, including plucking directly on piano strings, as well as clicking and scratching sounds, electronic tones and static, and sounds derived from recorded city noises and the chirps of grasshoppers and swallows.

Respectively, the five transpositions into music by Gunther Schuller, Peter Maxwell Davies, Giselher Klebe, Tan Dun, and Niklaus Erismann effectively realize Arthur Danto's suggestions: "Klee is making some kind of point about the futility of machines," "[o]r perhaps he is saying it might not be a bad thing if we bent our inventive gifts to the artificial generation of bird songs."⁵¹ But if this is music about birds, it is about birds that do not sing. These are musical offerings that do not remind us of nightingales or mockingbirds. Pierre Boulez thought it best to render the drawing as silence.⁵²

Can we see *music* in *Twittering Machine* and not just bird noises? Klee's simple pen-and-ink drawing, *Concert on the Branch* (FIG. 4) predates *Twittering Machine* by one year and it prefigures the

Fig. 4
Paul Klee, *Konzert auf dem Zweig*
[*Concert on the Branch*], 1921, 188, pen
on paper on cardboard, 28,2 x 22 cm,
Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern
© Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image
Archive

cluster of the four birds *nearly* exactly as it appears in *Twittering Machine*.

The branch connects organically to a tree trunk instead of the crank-and-shaft contraption. The rest of the *Twittering Machine* drawing composition is absent, except for the birds. So, the 1922 composition repeats the 1921 drawing, but without being an exact copy. The four birds are the very much same in both, and thus ostensibly just the way that Klee wanted them drawn and arranged. But the 1921 drawing shows a *concert*, not a *machine*. As Danto identifies them, the “quartet of screwy birds” by themselves thus comprise a concert, which would not be different when their perch is re-positioned above an “inert,” “benign” machine.⁵³ Indeed, a quartet.

MUSICIAN-ARTIST PAUL KLEE

Klee was a musician, a prodigy as a youth, and he played privately in string quartets and ensembles until illness late in life curtailed it.⁵⁴ Rainer Maria Rilke, who had collected Klee drawings, wrote in 1921: “Even if you hadn’t told me he plays the violin, I would have guessed that on many occasions his drawings were transcriptions of music.”⁵⁵

Klee’s violin-playing was passionate. “When playing the violin, Klee surrendered himself to music. His eyes became transfixed, and he appeared to lose all awareness of his surroundings.”⁵⁶

One of his ensemble partners extolled Klee’s precise accomplishment in performing Mozart:

“Klee could perform Mozart’s arabesques and little motifs with total precision and at the same time total warmth. His command of the pleasurable and exhilarating tension of Mozart’s music, of its formal perfection in search of blissful fulfillment, reflected the inimitable assurance of a divine gift.”⁵⁷

Klee’s affinity for the spirit of Mozart’s music, furthermore, strikes at the heart of Klee’s art.

“His Mozart playing went right to the heart of the matter. If Mozart’s essence may be described as a blend of demonic power, vivacious wit, and sensuality, then it may also be said that there is a genuine kinship between Mozart the musician and Klee the painter.”⁵⁸

There may be something in *Twittering Machine* that is about what it is to *play music*, to *perform in a musical ensemble*. Klee may well have meant something slightly different using the verb, *zwitschern*, from what gets translated in English as *twittering*. In 1898, at age nineteen, already doing art and performing music, he writes in his diary:

“Nature does love me! She consoles me and makes promises to me. On such days I am invulnerable. Outwardly smiling, inwardly laughing more freely, a song in my soul, a twittering whistle [zwitcherndes Pfeifen] on my lips, I cast myself on the bed, stretch, and keep watch over my slumbering strength.”⁵⁹ The word means: Emit a series of quickly repetitive, higher, often clear, buzzing, but mostly not very loud tones.⁶⁰ “Zwitchern: (von bestimmten Vögeln) eine Reihe rasch aufeinanderfolgender, hoher, oft hell schwirrender, aber meist nicht sehr lauter Töne von sich geben”⁶¹

Twittering for Klee is a matter of exulting and singing, rather than a forced mechanical chirping. Colloquially, *zwitchern* can mean to imbibe in an alcoholic drink, but pejorative connotations – tittering, giggling, chattering rapidly in a small voice – that attach to the English word do not inhere to the German counterpart.⁶² Twittering, as Klee used the word in his diary, evokes how, in the moment of *ekstasis*, the musician is transfixed, blocking out awareness of the surroundings, focused upon the precision of the performance, absorbed in the warmth of the expression. It is the song of one’s soul echoed in whistling. That is, it is not just from birds, and it is not mechanical noise.

THE FOUR BIRDS AND THE SEVEN BIRDS

Summing up so far: Paul Klee and Jerry Garcia both aspired to art and music in their youth, Klee choosing to pursue art seriously while enjoying musical performance, and Garcia the opposite; Garcia’s small drawing noted as a tribute to Paul Klee translates elements of *Twittering Machine* into a derivative but not imitative work; Klee’s inscriptions of the title of the drawing juxtaposes machine and twittering; Arthur Danto’s comments on *Twittering Machine* suggests a reading contrary to the more common perception that the

birds are driven by the machine; Klee’s *Concert on the Branch* shows the same drawing of birds enjoying their singing; Gilles Deleuze’s theory of diagrams contributes to a separation of the elements of machine and birds in the drawing; musical compositions representing the drawing alternatively portray mechanical bird noises or explore how musicians can emulate natural bird noises. Further, paying particular attention to the graphic content of the two works of art, we can see Garcia’s composition as free interpretation of Klee’s original, which in turn we can then see as depicting, metaphorically, a string quartet.

The four birds emit graphically-different textured representations of their sounds: “tear-drop shape, paisley shape, curved line and arrow head”.⁶³ Their heads point upwards, down, to one side, and to the other side. A quartet singing simultaneously yet with different timbres. The first bird on the left with mouth pointed skyward, tail feathers curled below like a tuxedo, lets loose a long, languorous, but perfectly-formed inverted water droplet – “full, eloquent, lustrous, calm, round, pure, open”. The second bird, shorter than the first, long hair flowing down, head pointed down, legs spread wide, lets loose a dangling, sinuously-curved, thick line – “mellow, thick, weighty, silky, muffled, dark, solemn”. The third bird, mustached and bearded, almost as tall as the first, head tilted slightly upward, a scarf circling around neck and shoulders, lets loose a simple line curving gently upward – “clear, flute-like, thin, whistling, soft, sweet”. The fourth bird, with long hair flowing down the back, also shorter than the first and third birds, lets loose an elegant, barbed arrow pointed directly horizontal – “dark, reedy, distinctive, austere, rough, powerful, robust”. And so, having borrowed selectively from the Vienna Symphony online lists of instrument sound characteristics, we have, from left to right: first violin,

cello, second violin, and viola.⁶⁴ And, of course, the arrangement in heights and postures reflects the relative ranges of the four instrumental parts of a string quartet. Paul Klee played in string quartets all his life, until illness curtailed his playing late in life.⁶⁵ Choosing art rather than music had been his difficult choice in his youth.⁶⁶ And of course that tall bird/musician on the left, stretched striving to span earth and heaven, “eyes [...] transfixed, [appearing] to lose all awareness of his surroundings,” – that is Klee.⁶⁷

The crank and its suggestive cranking are merely apparent – it is *as if the birds could be mechanized*, each playing exactly in tune and on the beat. A musician playing in an ensemble internalizes and follows the flow of the music to meld with the ensemble. Without needing the metronome or conductor’s cue, it only *seems as if it were mechanized*, as if the musicians were cranking it out. In truth, the ensemble playing relies upon expressive, mutually anticipated and felt dynamics of volume and tempo, upon phrasing and articulation. It is far from mechanical, though when a perfected performance is perceived casually it may seem smoothly mechanical. It requires every fragment of spirit and intellect to make the ensemble sound perfect. The birds clutch a curved branch in the drawing, consistent with volume and tempo dynamics that curve over time, in contrast to the metronomic strict time that is useful only while practicing to get the fingering down. Thus, it makes sense that Klee’s title for the drawing, *Die Zwitscher – Maschine*, juxtaposes twittering with a machine rather than subsumes the former into the latter. The posture of the first bird shows the firm but not taut physical control of the musician’s ability to perform precisely, oblivious to surroundings, such as is said of Klee when performing Mozart. The ensemble steps out to its own space, oblivious to the environment around it – which falls away from

their cognizance. But the ensemble is in truth rickety and contrived, just as Klee depicts it – always precariously on the edge of the ensemble becoming entangled in the beat and breaking down. That is why musicians rehearse – to get a feel for how they will be playing the piece together, working out the flow of those dynamics, and becoming absorbed in the performance. Getting the feel, working out the flow, that is, playing around within the elasticity of those dynamics – this is more intense than the performance, which is its summative recapitulation. But then, for the Grateful Dead, there were no rehearsals different from performances. Performances were rehearsals. Each performance of a song was practice for the next, and the cover of the previous. Their performances were fluid, interspersing songs with improvisational jams in long medleys.

Like his exuberant but precise performance of Mozart, Klee understood his artistic constructions as precise endeavors – *exakte versuche im bereich der kunst*: “To learn to see behind the façade, to grasp something in its roots, to recognize the underlying forces, to learn the pre-history of the visible, to unveil, to ground, to analyze.”⁶⁸

If that is how Klee thinks his art, then that is what we should be doing in viewing and studying it. That he understood the abstraction of his art as making visible,⁶⁹ we should not expect his art to transform what is deep into the façade; the meaning may not likely congeal in one quick glance. In a letter to his parents, during the period when his creativity was completing its shift from music to art, he declares his intent is not “to reflect surface appearances [but] to penetrate within [...] I mirror the very heart. I write words on the brow and around the corners of the mouth. My faces are truer than real ones.”⁷⁰

Grohmann observes how this detailed but intense expressionism is an affect of musicianship:

“The deeper we go into his work, the more we realize how rich it is in unique, inexplicable forms of beauty – phenomena analogous to those that lead us to attribute a sixth sense to the musician.”⁷¹

Going deeper into Klee’s drawing, we see this very important shift in reading it – a shift from focusing upon how the drawing somehow says something about mechanical birds to inverting the metaphoric content, how the twittering birds and the crank-mechanism are metaphors for something else, something much broader, which Deleuze and Guattari would suggest leads into how birds and people act somewhat governed by compulsion and complexes but also somewhat freely and imaginatively. Klee’s art is poetic, in the way that poetry evokes layers of meaning – harmonious, ironically inflected, and not completely without tension. The poetry that allows for the elaborate, but still precise, reading will perhaps not exclude other layers, though surely the strong reading plays most coherently into the expansiveness of the whole. The crank and birds are the most concrete elements of the drawing, and it is perhaps easiest to assume that the rest of the composition embellishes their meaning. However, *just because* these are the more evident elements, they better provide the *figure* of the metaphor, for which the *ground* is not actually present in the drawing, but only indicated in the way of metaphor – which is the usual case for metaphor. Deleuze frequently invoked what Klee took as a motto, “not to render the visible but to render visible.”⁷² Garcia’s tribute drawing leads us into this shift. For how he has transposed the composition, it is clear that the birds stand for musicians, and the contraption inheres in their means of ensemble.

Klee’s drawing playfully symbolizes the string quartet, Garcia’s the electric guitar

and drum band. The pseudo-circuit-drawing among the birds is ornately convoluted compared to the simple thin perch for Klee’s birds. Indeed, the musicians in the electric guitar band hear each other as mediated through microphones, amplifiers, loud speakers, and monitors – which is different from listening to one another acoustically in close proximity. The sound surrounds all of Garcia’s birds, in contrast to the location of soft sounds in the identifiably single instruments of the string quartet. The wind-up key in the back of the major bird locates the machine-like creation lop-sidedly with the leader of the band. There is a leader in the electric-guitar band, from whom direction in the ensemble’s creativity emanates, reverberating through the rest of the band. Of course, that big bird to the left is Garcia. But just as each of the birds has its place within the circuitry, that creativity is not singular; the reverberation is spontaneously shared; and in the birds’ improvisational chattering shared with one another each relies upon the context of time and tone in which to make music. Seven birds in the band may not be universal for rock ‘n’ roll, but the Grateful Dead did perform with seven musicians during periods of its history, sometimes with five, and sometimes six, including in 1985 when Garcia composed *Like Twittering Machine (For Paul Klee)*. As is the case with the crank handle in the Klee drawing, the wind-up key is immobile, indicating, perhaps a different sort of performance tension. Most rock ‘n’ roll bands schedule a concert tour after the release of a new album, and to feature tunes from that new album performed *exactly* as one can hear on the album. Audiences will sometimes know the tunes as studio productions so well that the slightest deviation of a single note played differently they will find aesthetically disappointing. That would be the burden of the wind-up key, a burden that plagues most rock ‘n’ roll bands perform-

ing live concerts. But the Grateful Dead performed improvisation, and their audience expected a new, expressive treatment of the well-known tunes every time.⁷³ That's how the Grateful Dead chose to perform, so, for the birds in Garcia's drawing, the wind-up key is inert. Nevertheless, the life of performing was not entirely free from alienating stress. The band's song, *Stella Blue* (a brand and model of electric guitar) – lyrics by Robert Hunter and composition by Jerry Garcia – enunciated both the ecstatic joys and unrelenting despair of a life of performing, indeed emoting those two affects *simultaneously*, particularly as Garcia sang the tune.

“All the years combine
They melt into a dream
A broken angel sings
From a guitar
In the end there's just a song
Comes crying like the night (wind)
Through all the broken dreams
And vanished years”⁷⁴

In a performance at Robert F. Kennedy Memorial Stadium, Washington, DC, June 14, 1991, that is, in his 27th year of 30 performing with the Grateful Dead, and in the 49th of his 53 years on this earth, Garcia sings the tune with a raspy voice, seemingly diminished in verve and strength. As sad as the voice may sound, it is a startlingly courageous and profound performance, austerely celebratory. At the end, Garcia shouts out the repeated concluding line, “Stella Blue,” ever so slightly differently each time, but each time insistently, as if to impress upon someone who does not hear and does not understand what all this means. And then, more passionately still, “Blue! Blue! Blue! Blue! Stella Blue!” – to urge that strident invocation to echo forever. It is a defiant, energetic, longing, celebratory, prayerful invocation – and the musician is for the duration of the song

unbowed by the progress of his age and infirmity. Beneath that insistence the soulful joyfulness of Garcia's music still persists, perhaps not as invulnerable as it once was, but not muffled either. The wind-up key from *Like Twittering Machine (For Paul Klee)* is there, as it always has been, and as it indeed always has been, it is the musician who internalizes what both propels and excites.

The connection between abstract machines and refrain in Deleuze and Guattari's *A Thousand Plateaus*, for which *Twittering Machine* is emblematic, can be one of tension and repression, or one of release and joy. Garcia's *Stella Blue* intertwines these two affects together into the passion of the performing musician, such as, as I have argued, also finds depiction in Klee's *Twittering Machine*. Deleuze and Guattari's conceptual apparatus is meant to elucidate human psychological and social behavior more productively than rigid structuralist theories. These are not concepts meant to be despised or celebrated in applicable instances. It is an approach of stoic sanguinity, with the flexibility to provide an account for the nuanced vagaries of human existence. Similarly, one can look at *Twittering Machine* and see torment and subjugation, or one can look at it and see joy and autonomy. Any actual metaphorical correlate of the concatenation depicted in the drawing could veer in either direction.

Central to the diagrammatic and figurative construction to both Klee's drawing and Garcia's drawing is the interchangeability of birds and musicians. Drawing upon Olivier Messiaen's writings, Deleuze and Guattari write:

“We can then say that the musician bird goes from sadness to joy or that it greets the rising sun or endangers itself in order to sing or sings better than another, etc.”⁷⁵

A Grateful Dead tune, *Bird Song*, equates musician-singer and bird – lyrics

Fig. 5
 Paul Klee, *Lied des Spottvogels* [*Song of the Mockingbird*], 1924, 66, oil transfer drawing and watercolor on paper on cardboard, 29,6/29,9 x 38,8/39,2 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern
 © Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image Archive

by Robert Hunter and composition by Jerry Garcia, intended as a tribute to Janis Joplin after her death. It is a lyrical, lingering tune, and the sentiment is both preserving and mournful.

“All I know is something like a bird
 within her sang
 All I know, she sang a little while
 and then flew on”⁷⁶

The band often performed the song with acoustic guitars, Garcia singing lead. Klee, as well, animated the bird musician: *Song of the Mockingbird* (FIG. 5).

A slender cartoon bird with long legs stretched to rest upon the bough of a tree drawn abstractly. A small bubble emerges from the bird’s beak – soft and delicate as is the mockingbird’s improvising refrain. Below, lying prone is the visage of a man emerging from a dream as day breaks, hands and legs busily fumbling to grasp the song in the air much as does a babe playing with a mobile dangling over its crib. The man’s face is drawn as a partial rendition of a violin.

If “Mozart’s [...] blend of demonic power, vivacious wit, and sensuality”

echoes in Paul Klee’s art, that blend also describes Jerry Garcia’s music, and his art as well.⁷⁷ Klee’s chosen epitaph, undauntedly mirthful regarding death, expresses the elusiveness of his drawings’ meanings.

“On this side I cannot be grasped,
 For I live as much
 With the dead
 As with those yet unborn.

A little closer to creation than usual
 And yet nowhere nearly close enough.”⁷⁸

That passage came June 29, 1940. Jerome John (“Jerry”) Garcia remained yet unborn until August 1, 1942.

1 Higashi 2005a; p. xvii; Hart 2005, p. x; Garcia 2005c, p. xix.

2 Garcia 2005a, p. xiii.

3 Higashi 2005a, p. xviii.

4 Hart 2005, pp. x–xi.

5 Higashi 2005b, p. 176.

6 Garcia 2005b, pp. 44, 52, 69, 70, 101, 121.

7 Higashi 2005c, p. 77.

8 Garcia 2005b, from the front cover overlay.

9 Garcia 2005b, p. 70.

- 10 Museum of Modern Art online notes, <https://www.moma.org/collection/works/37347> (last accessed February 28, 2023).
- 11 Garcia 2005b, p. 70.
- 12 See: Bruhn 2004, p. 34; Zdebik 2012, p. 91.
- 13 Lanchner 1987, p. 25.
- 14 Ibid.
- 15 See: Pierce Commens.
- 16 Ibid.
- 17 Ibid.
- 18 Klee 1948, p. 25.
- 19 Grohmann 1955, pp. 161–162, 182.; Schuback 2013, pp. 419–442; Klee 1948, p. 17.
- 20 Zdebik 2012, p. 91.
- 21 See: Deleuze 2003, pp. 83–85. See also: Deleuze/Guattari 1987, pp. 312, 344; Deleuze/Guattari 1994, pp. 165, 203.
- 22 Deleuze/Guattari 1987, pp. 142–143.
- 23 Ibid.; Deleuze/Guattari 1980, p. 177.
- 24 Grohmann 1955, pp. 86, 206.
- 25 See: Naubert-Riser 1988, pp. 70–71; Baumgartner 2016, p. 93; Friedewald 2011, p. 110; Düchting 2004, p. 54; Hall 1977, p. 15; Gale 2013; Viegas 2019, p. 2380.
- 26 Grohmann 1955, p. 171.
- 27 Lanchner 1987, p. 25.
- 28 Danto 1991, pp. 82, 85.
- 29 Ibid., p. 85.
- 30 Ibid.
- 31 Ibid., p. 84.
- 32 Ibid.
- 33 Deleuze/Guattari 1987, p. 310.
- 34 Ibid., pp. 312, 337, 342, 344, 346.
- 35 Ibid., pp. 334, 323; Deleuze/Guattari 1980, p. 412.
- 36 Buchanan 2021, pp. 19–20.
- 37 Deleuze/Guattari 1987, pp. 320, 316–317.
- 38 Garcia 2005b, pp. 52–53.
- 39 Higashi 2005c, p. 77.
- 40 Grohmann 1955, pp. 27, 29, 42 f; Zehnder 2005, p. 87; Vergo 2015, pp. 295 f.
- 41 Jardi 1991, p. 7; Grohmann 1955, pp. 26–27, 48–49.
- 42 Schuback 2013, p. 419, note 1; Grohmann 1955, p. 280; Osterwold 2015, p. 122; Sallis 2015, pp. 119–127.
- 43 Schuback 2013, pp. 421, 423, 426, 427, 428.
- 44 Ibid., p. 423.
- 45 Schuller 1962, pp. 24–39; Schuller 1998.
- 46 Liner notes, Schuller 1998.
- 47 Bruhn 2004, pp. 36–41.
- 48 Bruhn 2004, pp. 45–48.
- 49 Tan Dun 1995, pp. 38–43; Tan Dun 2014.
- 50 Erismann, 2018, p. 95.
- 51 Danto 1991, p. 84.
- 52 Quoted in Gartmann 2020, p. 15.
- 53 Danto 1991, p. 84.
- 54 Grohmann 1955, pp. 29, 70.
- 55 Jardi 1991, p. 8.
- 56 Grohmann 1955, p. 70.
- 57 Zehnder 2005, p. 88.
- 58 Ibid.
- 59 Klee 1968, p. 16 (entry 54); Klee 1957, pp. 27–28.
- 60 Translation by author.
- 61 Duden 2023.
- 62 Ibid., OED 1989.
- 63 Zdebik 2012, p. 92.
- 64 Vienna Symphonic Library, <https://www.vsl.co.at/en> (last accessed February 23, 2023).
- 65 Grohmann 1955, pp. 29, 70.
- 66 Baumgartner 2005, p. 176.
- 67 Grohmann 1955, p. 70.
- 68 Schuback 2013, p. 430, German: note 18.
- 69 Grohmann 1955, p. 181.
- 70 Ibid., p. 31.
- 71 Ibid., pp. 379–380.
- 72 Ibid., p. 181; Deleuze/Guattari 1987, pp. 342, 344. See also: Smith 2003, p. xxiii.
- 73 See: Weir 2022.
- 74 Dodd 2005, pp. 194–195.
- 75 Deleuze/Guattari 1987, p. 318.
- 76 Dodd 2005, p. 153.
- 77 Zehnder 2007, p. 88.
- 78 Güse 2001, p. 214.

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